

References

1. C. G. R. NAIR and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 239.
2. C. G. R. NAIR, R. LALITHAKUMARI and P. I. SENAN, *Talanta*, 1978, 25, 525.
3. C. P. KRISHNA PILLAI and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1980, 27, 751.
4. K. D. MAHILAMONY and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1981, 28, 627.
5. M. P. RADHAMMA and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1983, 30, 49.
6. P. INDRASENAN and M. P. RADHAMMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 729.
7. M. P. RADHAMMA and P. INDRASENAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 464.
8. T. OKADA, T. KAKUTANI and M. OGAWA, *Yuki Gosei Kagaku Kyokai Sh.*, 1957, 15, 295 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, 51, 13852).
9. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1964.
10. I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1957, Vol. III.

Search for Yeast Strains Suitable for Large-Scale Production of Fat : Effect of Nitrogen Deficiency on Accumulation and Composition of Fat in Some Yeasts

SRILATA BAGCHI†, JYOTIRMOY DUTTA*

and

SUDHAMOY GHOSH

Bose Institute, Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 3 November 1981, accepted 18 January 1985

THE search for a microbial source of fat, alternative to the conventional ones, viz. plant and animal, was initiated during the World War-II¹. In the face of the recent world wide shortage of fat this search has been revitalised and it has been found that yeasts are the most suitable organism for this purpose². While choosing a yeast strain suitable for large-scale production of fat, the most important property that has to be considered is its oleaginicity, i.e. its capacity to accumulate fat in the cells. Fat accumulation in oleaginous yeasts is known to be enhanced when grown in media of low nitrogen and high sugar content¹. As the possible uses of a fat is determined largely by its composition, this factor is also very important in the large-scale production of fat from yeasts. We report here the results of nitrogen starvation on accumulation and composition of fat in cells of two strains of yeast which have been isolated by us from local soil. Of these two, the red one was characterised and designated as *Rhodotorula glutinis* Y₃³, the other strain (white) was found to be a *Candida* species but was not further characterised⁴. The results were compared with those of seven other yeast strains obtained from the National Chemical Laboratories, Poona. The two media used for growth of the yeasts were,

(i) *Complex medium*: glucose, 20 g; peptone, 5 g; malt extract, 3 g dissolved in 1 l distilled water; pH adjusted between 6.4 and 6.6, and (ii) *Nitrogen negative medium*: glucose, 20 g; KH₂PO₄, 0.8 g; K₂HPO₄, 0.2 g; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.2 g; NaCl, 0.2 g; CaCl₂·2H₂O, 0.05 g; Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, 0.5 mg; Na₂WO₄·2H₂O, 0.5 mg; FeSO₄·7H₂O, 0.025 g dissolved in 1 l distilled water, pH adjusted between 6.4 and 6.6.

The yeast strains were grown in conical flasks (1 l) containing 250 ml of the complex medium on a gyratory shaker at 25° upto early stationary phase of growth. The cells were harvested by centrifugation at 4°, made free of nitrogenous materials by repeated washing with cold sterile water and centrifugation. A part of the washed cells were lyophilised and stored in deep-freeze for lipid extraction. A suitable portion of the rest of the washed cells was inoculated into the nitrogen-negative medium so that the cell density corresponded to an O.D. (590 nm) between 2 and 2.5. The cells were allowed to grow at 25° upto 96 h. The nitrogen starved cells were harvested, washed and lyophilised for fat extraction.

From a known amount of lyophilised cells, fat was extracted according to the method of Bagchi and Dutta⁵. Total phosphorous (mol %) in the fat was estimated according to the method of Ames⁶; this data was converted to weight percentage of total phospholipids (as distearoyl lecithin) on multiplication with a factor of 25.4. The non-polar components, i.e. triglycerides (TG), sterol-esters (SE), free fatty acids (FFA) and sterols were separated by tlc on silica gel G plates (preparative) developed in hexane-diethyl ether-acetic acid (80:20:1.5). The fluorescent bands due to these components, located by observing the chromatogram under uv-light after spraying lightly with a 0.2% methanolic solution of 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein, were scraped into small columns, their contents extracted with diethyl ether and isolated by removal of the solvent⁶. Sterols and SE were determined colorimetrically⁷. Mixed methylesters were prepared from TG and FFA by methanolysis in the presence of alkali⁸ and BF₃⁹, respectively. Percentages of TG and FFA were determined by glc of the corresponding mixed methyl esters with methylpentadecanoate added as internal standard¹⁰.

Under nitrogen starvation, the cells of most of the strains were found to accumulate higher amount of fat than under nitrogen sufficient condition (Table 1). This increase was most prominent in *R. glutinis* Y₃ (from 18.0 to 55.1%) followed by *L. starkeyi* (from 23.0 to 37.1%), the increases being 3.1 and 1.6 fold, respectively. A 3.5 fold increase in the fat accumulation was also observed with *H. anomala* cells but the final fat content was quite low (4.1%). In the cases of *S. cerevisiae* and the untyped *Candida* species cellular fat depleted due to nitrogen starvation. Thus *R. glutinis* Y₃ proves to be a yeast strain that can accumulate substantial amount of fat in the cells which increases to a very

†Present address: Elbert Einstein College of Medicine, Yeshiva University, Bronx, New York, 10461. U.S.A.

NOTES

TABLE 1—CELLULAR FAT CONTENT AND ITS COMPOSITION IN SOME YEAST STRAINS GROWN UNDER NITROGEN SUFFICIENCY AND NITROGEN STARVATION

Yeast strains ^a	Increase in O.D. (590 nm) of the culture under nitrogen starvation ^b	Composition of cellular fat											
		Fat content (%dry cell)		Phospholipids		Triglycerides		Sterols		Sterol esters		Free fatty acids	
		+N	-N	+N	-N	+N	-N	+N	-N	+N	-N	+N	-N
1. <i>Hansenula anomala</i> 3341	8.4	4.1	14.3	14.0	18.5	43.6	56.3	5.0	4.7	2.6	3.5	26.7	10.4
2. <i>Hansenula suaveolens</i> 3277	10.6	9.1	9.4	15.4	17.6	37.5	50.7	4.9	5.8	5.1	1.6	29.0	21.2
3. <i>Torula utilis</i> 3055	10.4	5.0	9.8	13.6	17.2	36.7	49.7	4.8	8.7	6.0	7.3	32.7	9.1
4. <i>Torulopsis lipofera</i> 3252	6.3	6.2	11.6	9.7	17.7	40.7	56.7	5.1	3.8	5.1	3.8	30.1	10.4
5. <i>Rhodotorula glutinis</i> Y ₃	8.0	17.7	55.1	9.3	1.9	64.0	85.0	4.0	4.4	1.2	0.1	17.2	6.6
6. <i>Lipomyces starkeyi</i> 3440	11.4	23.0	37.1	6.3	3.0	76.2	89.3	4.3	0.9	0.2	0.1	8.7	2.0
7. <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> 3190	4.4	14.3	6.4	12.5	3.4	24.9	42.0	9.6	5.4	22.0	36.5	23.9	9.2
8. <i>Candida lipolytica</i> 3229	8.4	4.0	5.2	9.6	16.4	34.8	54.2	6.2	7.3	2.9	1.3	15.3	12.1
9. <i>Candida</i> (untyped)	6.9	9.7	8.0	18.1	20.0	43.4	52.0	5.5	5.3	7.5	5.7	22.3	9.0

^aStrain 1-4 and 6-8 obtained from National Chemical Laboratories, Poona ; strain 5 and 9 isolated from local soil.

^bO.D. (590 nm) of culture adjusted between 2 and 2.5 at inoculation.

+N=Cells grown under nitrogen sufficiency.

-N=Cells grown under 96 h of nitrogen starvation.

large extent with 96 h of nitrogen starvation surpassing *L. starkeyi* which is well known as a oleaginous yeast^{11,12}.

The class compositions of the accumulated fats presented in the Table 1, do not add upto 100% ; this is because only some major components that could be unambiguously identified were measured. Glycolipids and diglycerides which may contribute to a small extent towards the total fat were not estimated. The class compositions of the fats, accumulated under nitrogen sufficient condition, in most of the strains are basically similar in nature, characterised by phospholipids (PL) between 9.6 and 18.1% ; TG between 34.8 and 43.6% ; FFA between 15.3 and 32.7%, and low sterol (maximum 6.2%) and SE (maximum 7.5%) levels. But the compositions of the fats from *R. glutinis* Y₃, *L. starkeyi* and *S. cerevisiae* were to a considerable extent different from the rest. The fats from the first two strains are characterised by very high percentages of triglycerides (64 and 76.2%) and very low level of SE (1.2 and 0.2%). The fat derived from *S. cerevisiae* differs from all other strains in that it contains almost equal amounts of TG (34.9%) and SE (22.0%).

The remarkable general effect of nitrogen starvation on the composition of the fats is the increase in the percentage of TG. Again this effect is very prominent in *R. glutinis* Y₃ (from 64 to 85%) and comparable only with *L. starkeyi* (76.2 to 89.3%). In the untyped *Candida* species

the increase in TG was small (from 43.4 to 52%). In *S. cerevisiae* the percentages of both TG and SE increased due to nitrogen starvation.

By virtue of the presence of over 85% TG which can be increased further by simply removing the FFA (refining), the fat from nitrogen starved *R. glutinis* Y₃ cells may be considered to be a suitable source for large scale production of fat.

References

1. M. WOODBINE, in "Progress in Industrial Microbiology", ed. D. J. D. HOCKENHULL, Heywood & Co. Ltd., London, 1959, Vol. I, p. 179.
2. D. A. WHITWORTH and C. RATLEDGE, *Process Biochem.*, 1974, 9, 14.
3. S. BAGCHI and J. DUTTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 726.
4. S. BAGCHI, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Calcutta, 1978.
5. B. N. AMES, in "Method in Emzymology", eds. E. NEUFELD and N. GINSBURG, Academic Press, 1966, Vol. VIII, p. 115.
6. E. LITCHFIELD, "Analysis of Triglycerides", Academic Press, New York, 1972, p. 22.
7. J. DUTTA, A. BISWAS, S. SAHA and C. DEB, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1976, 124, 29.
8. H. BROKERHOFF, *J. Lipid Res.*, 1965, 6, 10.
9. L. D. METCALF and A. A. SCHMITZ, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 33, 363.
10. M. L. BLANK, B. VERDINO and O. S. PRIVETT, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 42, 87.
11. R. L. STARKEY, *J. Bacteriol.*, 1946, 51, 33.
12. T. SUZUKI, A. TAKIGAWA and K. KASEGAWA, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1973, 37, 2653.